

The Influence Of Korean Nursing Students' Experience Of Major Converged Short-Term Study Abroad Program On Their Future Overseas Career Plans In The U.S

Hyo Geun Geun

Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>Purpose: The aim of this study was to describe nursing students' overseas hospital practice and language experiences hosted by B college in the US and examine how those experiences might influence the intent of double degree application and NCLEX-RN exam trials of students. Methods: A self-report online survey was completed by 33 nursing students at C university located in a city in Jeollanamdo. Data were analyzed by descriptive statistics, chi-square, t-test, and ANOVA. Results: Significant differences were found in the trial intentions of double degree and license exam by program year, the experience of language learning, and self-evaluated language fluency before program initiation. Participatory motivation, core competency, and general satisfaction with the program were significantly correlated with each other. In addition, the students who planned to take the exam were more motivated with the program participation than the other students. Conclusion: The nursing student's overseas major converged short-term experience had a positive impact on their future plans toward overseas employment and advanced academic careers. The study findings can be used as a guideline for the development of educational programs for the students' overseas career plans and strategies.</i></p>
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Introduction

Since the 1990s, many universities have sent students outside Korea to get them to take the global program through MOU contracts with universities^[1-3] These trends were sped up by national policies such as globalization and English education crazily so-called.^[4]

Those overseas experiences are often confused in their terms and used interchangeably with others: global volunteer,^[5] exchange student programs,^[6] overseas hospital practice,^[7] global health capacity,^[8] and study abroad.^[3,9] Regardless of those terms, until recently, 200,000 students per year have moved to other countries.^[10]

Recently, the characteristics of these phenomena have changed from simply overseas experiences into participation in the major converged program in order to build up a consistent cooperating body with universities and practical institutions from the university's point of view. Several studies reported that these experiences actually impacted student's life through unfamiliar and new experiences.^[1,2,11] In addition, these experiences are expected to make students attain opportunities for future overseas employment.^[2]

Although the number of students in nursing who went abroad was relatively low compared with those from other disciplines such as language or business major, many nursing departments have tried to cooperate and share with other universities outside Korea, especially developed countries, in order to provide a variety of hospital practice and advanced nursing education, ultimately leading our students to cope with rapidly changing globalization by having a sense of international perspective and foreign language fluency.^[12]

Regarding nursing students' overseas experiences, most studies published in Korea are conducted qualitatively based on grounded theory^[2] or various phenomenological methodologies,^[1,6,11,13] and even topic modeling.^[10] In addition, studies on the effects of overseas experiences are mostly focused on the development of language skills and intercultural sensitivities.^[14] There have been still pros and cons in terms of explaining their meanings, positively or negatively.

For example, a study reported Korean nursing students' overseas experiences in the U.S. 8 nursing students in D college, who were selected with higher English and GPA scores than other students, participated in the program with their professor. They actually participated in the simulation practice. After the program, they were in-depth intervened three times in order to explain and describe their experiences.^[2] Their experiences were categorized into several areas such as new experiences, living as the organizers of life, and finding themselves in another me. This program in general seemed to impact positively the student's life, and live as they planned for some time. Another positive impact is that some of the students were willing to prepare

NCLEX-RN exam along with their regular school curriculum.^[1] This study extracted 25 meanings from five themes based on 8 students' experiences such as a desire to experience the new world, faced with a language barrier. These students were experienced in a university located in the state of Georgia for four weeks. As such, these students also expressed both sides' feelings: positive for academic and practical environments for students and nurses and negative for slow processing of duties and so on. Regarding negative feelings, throughout studies, most students reported their language barrier^[1,11,12] while participating in overseas programs. That is, English fluency was one of the concerns most students had before abroad and in actual reality there. Many of them took English fluency as the barrier^[15] for program participation and recognized the necessity of English learning.^[12]

Relevant studies using quantitative methods are very few. However, those studies have reported valuable evidence. For example, nursing students' professionalism, global health competency, and critical thinking dispositions after participating global leadership program^[15] or global health capacity-building program^[8] significantly increased. Additionally, the participating students more got interested in the global movement to outside Korea for future overseas employment or applications of academic advanced programs after overseas experiences while they were students regardless of the length of programs.^[1-3] That is, the students seemed to take the experiences as the turning point of their life, not limited to the current boundary. A previous study's findings supported those trends that students' intention for migration, stress, and social recognition was related to their overseas employment, and 55.9% of students responded positively to the intention.^[16] In sum, one of the positive effects of overseas experiences is that, whether the period is short or not, the students became dreaming of the global movement outside Korea and took the experiences as a critical point of their lives.

In the nursing area, very few studies have examined the relationships between nursing students' overseas experiences and overseas employment intention based on the experiences.^[10] Most studies regarding overseas training were mainly reports about language courses or English education.^[2] Very few studies investigated nursing students' life after overseas experiences or experiences themselves. Therefore, we believe that this study provides valuable information regarding uncovered relationships or variables that could predict the willingness of nursing students for global movements. The findings of this study can be applied to the development of global programs at the university level for overseas employment opportunity enhancement.

Term Definition

For this study, the short-term study abroad which was a major converged program is defined as a temporary journey undertaken in the U.S. for educational purposes during pre-defined periods except for regular degree progress, overseas volunteers, working holidays, and so on.^[10]

Purpose

This study aims to explore the learning experiences of university nursing students who had taken the global leadership program at B college in the U.S., and their intention to apply for double degree academic programs and NCLEX-RN exam after graduation. This study will be of benefit to nursing students who plan to apply for the overseas program or employment abroad in the future as a guideline. Specific objectives are:

- 1) describe the general characteristics of students
- 2) examine the general satisfaction of students with the current programs
- 3) investigate the related variables for applications for both academic programs overseas or exams for overseas employment.

Method

Study Design

This study was a cross-sectional quantitative descriptive study covering the 2019-2020 winter global challenge projects arranged by C university. A total of 33 students (13 from 2019, and 20 from 2020) participated in the program. Self-administered questionnaires were given through a web survey and completed by the participants. The questionnaires are composed of 4 sections: 1) demographic characteristics, 2) the perceived level of participatory motivations and program environments, 3) the achieved level of core competency, and 4) the relationship between significant variables and intention of NCLEX-RN exam trial and applying for a double degree. A total of 39 items were included. All participants answered the survey questions appropriately.

Sample

For this purpose, this study collected 33 reports from the students at a C university who participated in its 2-week study abroad program including practical experiences hosted by B college in the U.S. They were all 3rd grade at that time and comprised of 4 males and 29 female students in the department of nursing, C university located in Jeollanamdo. The selection criteria include 1) a TOEIC score taken any time by then while in university, 2) a previous semester grade over 3.5 out of 4.5, and 3) agreement to an in-depth interview two

times by nursing professors. 13 students for the 2019 year and 20 students for the 2020 year were selected through these multi-staged selection process. After the program, a website for the survey was given to all participants. All of them completed the survey, and the confidentiality and anonymity of responses were assured.

2-week leadership Programs

The program was held in January 2019 and 2020, respectively, and composed of two sections: English learning from native lectures for 1 week and nursing practice in a hospital for the other week in two separate hospitals located in New Jersey. The contents and schedules of the global leadership program were absolutely arranged by B college, International Training and Professional Studies.

Measures

General characteristics: This part includes 8 questions: program year, gender, GPA attained in the last semester, the highest score of TOEIC, the overseas experience for vacation or study purposes, the experience of language learning, and self-evaluation of English proficiency attained before program participation.

The level of participatory motivations and environments of global projects program: This tool was developed by authors to investigate students' perceived difference between motivations and performance of motivations and environments before and after participation in the overseas programs.^[9] A higher score means an increased level of motivation. Of the tool areas, we used the participatory motivation tool only for this study, which was composed of 19 items. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was .87 for this study.

The achieved level of core competency: C university established eight fundamental core competencies and required all students to achieve them until graduation. All students need to take part in various programs provided by the C university to verify their competencies. From the university's perspective, students' participation in the programs is also the opportunity for evaluation of the programs. The tool is composed of 8 questions: thinking ability, utilizing ability, leading ability, interaction ability, personal relation ability, and global (global and local) ability. The core competence was measured using a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). A higher score indicated a higher level of core competency. Observed Cronbach's alpha coefficient for this study was .89.

General satisfaction of the program: This tool was developed by the professor leading this program and composed 4 items: perceived level of satisfaction for the English program, hospital practice, weekend activities, and individual visits to New York, respectively. The answers were rated using a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). A higher score indicated that nursing students were highly satisfied with the program in general. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was .69 in the present study.

Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed with SPSS/WIN (21.0 version). P-values of < .05 were considered to be statistically significant. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the general characteristics of participants and the levels of measured variables. T-tests and analysis of variance were done to compare the dependent variable according to the general characteristics. The associations among the three measured variables were estimated with Pearson correlations. Lastly, T-tests were conducted to compare the dependent variables according to the major independent variables

Results

Sample characteristics

As shown in Table 1, by the year, 13 students participated in the program held in 2019, whereas 20 students participated in 2020 (39.4% vs 60.6%). There were 4 male (12.1%) and 29 female (87.9%) students among the respondents. About half of percentage (45.5%) of respondents attained over a 4.0 GPA in the last semester. 69.8% of students received a TOEIC score of over 600 (middle or high level) out of 990. Except for 4 students, most students reported at least one experience of overseas travel only, whereas only 75.8% of respondents went abroad for language training. For the self-evaluated level of language fluency, 'average' answers were from 24.2% of the respondents before program initiation, whereas 78.8% reported improved language fluency after the program. Their satisfaction with the programs was reported by almost all participants (97.0%).

Table 1. General characteristics of Participants (N= 33)

Characteristics	Categories	n (%)	Double degree			NCLEX-RN exam		
			Yes(n=19)	No(n=14)	p-value*	Yes(n=18)	No(15)	p-value*
Year	2018	13 (39.4)	12 (63.2)	1 (7.1)	.001	4 (22.2)	9 (60.0)	038

Gender	2019	20 (60.6)	7 (36.8)	13 (92.9)		14 (77.8)	6 (40.0)	
	male	4 (12.1)	1 (5.3)	3 (21.4)	.160	2 (11.1)	2 (13.3)	.846
GPA in the last semester	female	29 (87.9)	18 (94.7)	11 (78.6)		16 (88.9)	13 (86.7)	
	2.5≤	5 (15.2)	4 (21.1)	1 (7.1)	.545	2 (11.1)	3 (20.0)	.380
TOEIC score	3.5≤	13 (39.4)	7 (36.8)	6 (42.9)		9 (50.0)	4 (26.7)	
	4.0≤	15 (45.5)	8 (42.1)	7 (50.0)		7 (21.2)	8 (53.3)	
	low	10 (30.3)	4 (21.1)	6 (42.9)	.122	5 (27.8)	5 (33.3)	.357
Experience in overseas travel	middle	19 (57.6)	11 (57.9)	8 (57.1)		12 (66.7)	7 (46.7)	
	high	4 (12.1)	4 (21.1)	0		1 (3.0)	3 (20.0)	
	1-2	17 (51.5)	10 (52.6)	7 (50.0)	.674	10 (55.6)	7 (46.7)	.449
Experience of language learning	3≤	12 (36.4)	6 (31.6)	6 (42.9)		5 (27.8)	7 (46.7)	
	none	4 (12.1)	3 (15.8)	1 (7.1)		3 (16.7)	1 (6.7)	
Self-eval. of foreign language fluency (pre)	1-2	25 (75.8)	13 (68.4)	12 (85.7)	.252	17 (94.4)	8 (53.3)	.006
	none	8 (24.2)	6 (31.6)	2 (31.6)		1 (5.6)	7 (46.7)	
Self-eval of foreign language fluency (post)	not good	25 (75.8)	12 (63.2)	13 (92.9)	.049	16 (88.9)	9 (60.0)	.054
	≥ average	8 (24.2)	7 (36.8)	1 (7.1)		2 (11.1)	6 (40.0)	
General satisfaction of program	not good	7 (21.2)	5 (26.3)	2 (14.3)	.403	4 (22.2)	3 (20.0)	.876
	≥ average	26 (78.8)	14 (73.7)	12 (85.7)		14 (77.8)	12 (36.4)	
	<average	1 (3.0)	0	1 (7.1)	.237	1 (5.6)	0	.354
	≥ average	32 (97.0)	19 (100.0)	13 (92.9)		17 (94.4)	15 (100.0)	

* *t* or F analysis applied

Descriptive Statistics and Correlations Among the 3 Major Variables (Participatory motivation, Core-Competency, and General Satisfaction)

Table 2 presents the mean scores of the three measurements used. Among them, general satisfaction for the program had the highest mean score (4.59±0.38) followed by achieved core competency (4.37±0.41). Compared to these two variables, the score for motivation had a little lower level (4.13±0.37).

Table 2. Perceived Levels of Participatory Motivation, Core-Competency, and General Satisfaction

Variables	M ± S.D.	Range	Reliability
Participatory motivation	4.13 ± 0.37	3.37 - 4.84	0.871
Core Competency	4.37 ± 0.41	3.75 - 5.00	0.885
General Satisfaction	4.59 ± 0.38	3.50 - 5.00	0.685

Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to determine the relationships among the three variables (Table 3). The participatory motivation was moderately correlated with core competence ($r = .67$, $p < .01$) followed by general satisfaction with the program ($r = .53$, $p < .01$). In addition, there was a moderate level of correlation between core competence and general satisfaction for the program ($r = .46$, $p < .01$).

Table 3. Correlations among Participatory Motivation, Core-Competence, and General Satisfaction

Variables	Motivation	Core Competence	General Satisfaction
Participatory motivation	1		
Core-Competence	.67**	1	
General Satisfaction	.53**	.46**	1

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Associations Between Selected Demographic Characteristics and the 2 Variables (Intention for the Double Degree and NCLEX-RN exam trial)

Table 1 shows the demographic and academic characteristics that were significantly related to the intention of either a double degree or an NCLEX-RN exam trial. For both trials, there were significant differences in program year ($p < .001$ in 2019, and $p = .038$ in 2020). The group consisting of nursing students in 2019 was more likely to 'Yes' for the double degree trial but 'No' for the other trial as compared with the other year's respondents. For the NCLEX-RN exam trial, the answers of students in 2020 were inversely directed. Intention for the double degree trial had significant relationships with self-evaluated English fluency before initiation of the program ($p = .049$). Students who self-evaluated their language fluency as 'not good' were more likely to report 'No' for the double-degree trial. That is, for advanced academic carrier development, students may regard language ability as the priority needed for the study. Significant differences were observed in the number of experiences for language training with the intention for the NCELX-RN exam trial ($p = .006$). Students who had experience with overseas language training planned to apply for overseas employment.

Comparative Statistics of 3 Major Variables According to the Trials

As shown in Table 4, differences in applying intentions for double degree and NCLEX-RN exam trials were tested according to variables: participatory motivation, core competence, and general satisfaction. A significant difference in students' NCLEX-RN exam trials was found in participatory motivation ($p = .036$). Those students who showed their intentions for the exam trials were more likely to report higher motivation scores with the program participation compared with the students who did not want to take the exams.

Table 4. Comparison of the Trials Intention for Double Degree and the NCEX-RN Exam according to Participatory motivation, Core-Competency, and General Satisfaction of Program

Characteristics	Double degree				NCLEX-RN exam			
	Yes (n=19)	No (n=14)	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Yes (n=18)	No (15)	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Participatory motivation	4.21	4.02	1.537	.135	4.28	4.01	2.195	.036
Core competency	4.47	4.23	1.732	.093	4.26	4.51	1.825	.078
General Satisfaction	4.65	4.51	1.040	.307	4.53	4.67	1.061	.297

Discussion

In the present study, all of the nursing students experienced overseas hospitals for the first time in their life. It is also their first experience meeting foreign medical and nursing personnel and taking care of foreign people even for a very short time. They felt the expansion of their perspective and thoughts on nursing professionalism, got the mind that they can advance into the world, and enlarged their dream. To some extent, this is a similar experience of nurses caring for foreign patients.^[6,17]

As it is evidenced in the literature, the foreign language fluencies of students who participated in this program were improved: the number of students who self-evaluated English fluency as 'over or average' increased from 8 students (24.2%) to 26 students (78.8%). In addition, the students who considered their fluency as 'over or average' were more likely to have the intention for the double-degree trial ($p = .049$), but not the NCLEX-RN exam. It is assumed that the students seemed to feel that the double degree program requires more fluent language fluency than the other trial which was just considered a paper-based exam: thus, it can be overcome with their efforts. In a similar sense, students who had no experience in language learning rarely got the intention to the exam trial ($p = .006$). It seems to be true that language fluency has something to do with the choice, no matter what the choice the students have abroad for the future, although there are still cons and pros like below.

The students who participated in the global programs were mostly selected due to their high GPA and TOEIC score first.^[1-2] It sounded awkward to some extent because the purpose of the global program was to increase their level of language fluency because it is the strongest barrier.^[1,12,15] Therefore, the purpose of the program was often vague in the real progress of the program. In addition, the language proficiency of the student was not correlated to their participatory motivations for the overseas internship programs: that is, language competency was not the main barrier to the stage of application for the programs.^[18]

In a similar sense, there is a study suggesting students need to be more careful in choosing language training because language training experience had a significant effect on the average wage, not the full-time first job.^[19] There is a still lack of evidence that overseas experiences are closely correlated with employment abroad. However, we were used to more believe that overseas experiences had a positive effect on student's life. A recent research^[2] reported that students had a desire to work abroad after training in the U.S. General college students who went through short-term language training also said that their desire to move around the world was strengthened after the training. Therefore, further research is required to decide which part can be the main role in the selection criteria for overseas programs or employment

As assumed, motivated students for overseas experiences are more likely to be satisfied with the programs provided and achieve core competencies. In the current study, the three major variables are correlated with each other and make the others increase. In particular, nursing students' core competencies such as interpersonal competence, communication competence, global competency, and understanding ability of cultural diversity were improved after the program; ranging from 4.61 to 4.21 out of 4.5 (Mean = 4.38). It was not possible to compare their values before and after the program, however, the values of core competencies are close to an average level. This finding is similar to the results of previous studies.^[8,15] which included the improvement of global health competency or global health capacity. It seemed that after the programs, regardless of the program periods, most participating students dreamed of outgoing abroad based on their improved competencies. Thus, more programs and studies are needed to evaluate the improved level of nursing students' competencies in regard to global leadership projects in universities.

Regarding the intention for a double degree, the students in 2019 were significantly more likely to show their intentions compared to the students in 2020 ($p = .001$). On the contrary, the results for the intention of NCLEX-RN exam trials were reversely reported: the students in 2020 had more trial intentions for the exams than the other year's students participated ($p = .038$). It is believed that the students in 2020 might have more information about each trial than the earlier students: double degree pragmas are expensive, however, NCLEX-RN exams are relatively inexpensive and can be taken at any time when they want.

In a similar vein, a significant difference in participatory motivation was found between Yes-respondents and No-respondents in the intention of the NCLEX-RN trial exam ($t = 2.195$, $p = .036$), but not in the other trial. Students seemed to take that the license exam is more realistically feasible than participating in the double degree program in consideration of expenses and periods required, and so on.

There were still very few studies explaining the variables related to the intention of overseas employment, especially targeting nursing students. A study^[16] identified that condition, social cognition, competition, and job searching stress were significantly correlated with nursing students' intention of employment abroad. Not exactly but similarly, the result of this finding is supporting the previous evidence. Students who participated in overseas programs are more positively affected in their lives, and some of them actually planned to move forward next steps based on these experiences.^[1,2,12]

In consideration of the expenses spent by school and students, time and efforts of students, there is a necessity for the development of appropriate measurements evaluating the achievements and results, leading to the enhancement of the programs.^[10]

Limitations and Recommendations

There were a number of limitations associated with the result of the interpretation of this study. Due to the nature of the cross-sectional study, we could not find any causal relationships between the trials and related variables. Moreover, we collected the pre-post self-evaluated language fluency at the same time, leading to confusion in answering questions. In addition, we could not exactly define the participatory motivations for our study purpose. As expected, Language fluency took a part in a role to some extent to decide on trials from students' perspectives as well as selecting prospective students from institutional perspectives. However, we still do not know well about the role of language fluency in this study. Last, we could not prove whether or not the students actually applied for the degree or exam as they had intended. For these study purposes, longitudinal studies are needed.

Surely, many students will continue to study, clinical practice, or volunteer abroad in the future. Considering that overseas training requires significant financial and administrative costs, as well as students' time and effort, it is important to systematically analyze overseas training experiences to increase program accountability.

In addition, beyond the positive effect such as improving language fluency improvement, the opportunities for future academic professional lives, self-awareness, self-growth, achievement, and self-identity through overseas training are recognized.^[3,8,11,13,20,21]

Conclusion

In the current study, among the selected variables, the experience of language learning and self-evaluated foreign language fluency were related to applying intention for the double degree or NCLEX-RN exams. It is supporting evidence that language is the most powerful facilitator as well as the strongest barrier. In addition, motivation for program participation was related to trial intention for the NCLEX-RN exam rather than the double degree. It seemed the NCLEX-RN exam is more realistically acceptable to students.

There is a still lack of research on overseas experiences in nursing.^[12] This study will provide new insight into the overseas experience of nursing students while in college based on an overall understanding of the nursing student' experience of participating in overseas short-term practical experience and contribute to developing the nursing curriculum based on the nursing student's overseas experience.

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Author Information

Hyo GeunGeun

Chodang University, Department of Nursing
 380, Muanro, Muaneup, Muangun, Jeollanamdo
 South Korea [58530]
